

DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH OF STUDENTS IN PRIMARY SCHOOL NATIVE LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract. *This article reflects on the emphasis on the speech development of primary school students through native language classes.*

Keywords: *speech development, primary education, native language, language elements, vocabulary.*

The development of speech of primary school students is an important problem of modern linguistic education. Primary education is a special stage in the life of a student of the early school age, associated with changes in his activities, mastering a new social role and expanding communicative ties. Also, the formation of broad language elements in students of this period, the use of visual and expressive capabilities of Uzbek language, the education of respect for the word, the development of creative potential and communicative competence are considered very important aspects.

It is known that primary education focuses on the formation of a common culture, cognitive development, and, on this basis, it should be said that primary education provides the basis for the independent implementation of the capabilities of the individual, and also ensures the social success of a person in the context of an information society.

Every individual highly educated, well-versed in the language can achieve great success, because today's sharp changes in the processes of globalization, its boundaries of thinking and opportunities for the manifestation of creative abilities are expanding.

Recently, changes have occurred in connection with the man-made nature of the development of society, the large-scale introduction of electronic means into life. New types of written speech have appeared, for example, real-time conversation, as well as various electronic forums and conferences, where modern schoolchildren spend a lot of time, are clear evidence of this. To convey maximum information, a person reduces the use of language tools, as a result of which his speech becomes much poorer and less expressive.

Ongoing changes require innovation and additions to the issues of improving lesson processes on the native language, and new approaches to the development of new programs and implementation of priority content, as well as new forms of work that reflect the continuity of traditions and the need for innovation. Today, teaching is viewed from the teacher to the student not as a simple translation of knowledge, but as cooperation, and in the educational process, methods of work begin to prevail, which ensure the formation of an independent creative personality, ready to perceive and solve innovative problems. Therefore, today primary education is faced with large and serious tasks, the maximum use of the capabilities of the methodology of teaching Uzbek language and literature in order not only to return respect for the word, but also to find effective and modern ways of developing students' speech, compliance with variability is recognized today as a fundamentally necessary feature of educational policy.

The curricula and teaching aids for the development of speech of primary classes take into account, first of all, the requirements of professional mobility and continuing education and are

called upon to carry out tasks for the implementation of cognitive, socio-cultural goals. The success of the work on the development of student speech can be carried out regularly, consistently and in the system, if it has an educational character.

For the period of education at the moment, the relevance of the development of students' speech in primary school native language lessons is determined by the social significance of the problems that determine the importance of improving speech literacy and speech culture of primary school students. And this problem determines the conflict between the requirements for the school curriculum and the real level of speech development of primary education students.

On this basis, the theory and practice of the methodology of education and upbringing seeks a worthy answer to the following issues:

how to improve the process of developing speech of primary school students, to form motivation for learning,

to create technologies aimed at developing and activating the creative abilities of students, also, to develop teaching aids with the involvement of new didactic material in order to update and develop speech competence of elementary school students;

in addition to mastering the rules of normative speech and developing speech skills, they also contribute to the development of the creative potential of primary school students, to the further development of speech skills, and to the formation of the ability to learn.

All this serves to perfectly organize the work of the development of the speech of students in elementary class native language lessons. It can be added that the subject of native language in primary classes serves to expand the thinking activities of young children, to develop skills and qualifications that contribute to the ability to think freely, listen to the opinion of others, fluently state their thoughts orally and in writing, and freely communicate with members of society. In this regard, teaching the native language is considered not as a teaching subject, but as an educational process that organizes the entire educational system. Speech is the use of thinking based on the type of activity of a person, the means of language (word, vocabulary, sentence). Speech acts as interaction and message, expressing one's own opinion with emotion, and influencing others. Well-developed speech serves as one of the most important tools of a person's activity in society. Based on this, speech for a student can be recognized as a weapon of successful education in school.

In the content of the current methodological literature, decisive solutions are given based on various approaches to the issue of growing the speech of elementary students. From the linguistic concepts included in the primary school native language program, the range of speech knowledge of students is expanded based on the separation of exercises into phonetic, lexical, word-making, morphemic (word composition), graphic, orthographic, orthoepic, grammatical exercises.

Also, the analysis carried out on the basis of such exercises is comprehensive in terms of helping elementary students to master theoretical concepts, enrich their vocabulary, grow their connected speech, as well as plays a role in ensuring students' comprehensiveness of the language. It should be further noted that it is also difficult to delve into the content of the exercise texts in the textbooks of the native language in primary classes, the analysis of the questions and tasks developed on them, the fact that they have the opportunity to grow the speech of students evolutionarily. While all exercise texts in native language textbooks help to strengthen and expand theoretical knowledge, it is also a prerequisite for students to enrich their vocabulary, grow their speech, practical mastery of the language, that exercises do not acquire perfection as a system, and

the structure of the exercises from national, textual statements intended to provide theoretical information will undoubtedly cause a decrease.

Students' speech competencies are polished during speech activities carried out in all the linguistic communities in which they exist, namely: in their own family, in the circle of peers, in social environments, since the reader, respectively, takes the position of both a speaker and a listener, participates in questions and answers as an active participant in the process, reacts, feels, uses the words that have been read and mastered in practice.

As a summary of the ideas, it should be noted that the theoretical foundations of the methodology for developing the speech of primary school students, considering the new educational environment, determine the laws for organizing educational material based on certain principles for speech development, identify and implement functional knowledge. These include:

- Textocentric: Utilizing the capabilities of language within the text.
- Hermeneutics: Understanding and interpreting the text.
- Activity-based: Beyond joint activities, this highlights the independent activities of both the teacher and students.
- Communicative: Awareness of the dialogic form of lesson organization and the role of students in communication.

Taking into account the continuity of traditions and the necessity for innovative approaches, it is appropriate to develop and shape a methodological system aimed at enhancing the speech of primary school students. This system should focus on improving speech abilities, enriching vocabulary, activating creative skills, and enhancing communicative competence.

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